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Fuzzy-FMEA for Risk Analysis: Decommissioning an Offshore Manifold Wellhead Platform

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Abstract. Decommissioning is the process of dismantling a portion or all of an installation and transporting the disassembled materials to a specific location. To manage the possible and impact of risks that might arise during the decommissioning process, risk analysis is carried out. In this study, a risk assessment was conducted on the decommissioning of a four-legged jacket platform. The analysis method used was Fuzzy Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (fuzzy-FMEA), which uses a fuzzification process to identify the dominant risks and generate fuzzy-RPN (FRPN). It was found that residual hydrocarbon leakage was the dominant risk with FRPN 9, and further risk analysis was carried out using Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) to identify the root causes of the dominant risk, which were planning errors with probability 0,00026645 and Sealing failures occur with a probability of 0.00044118. Bowtie Analysis was used as a risk management tool, resulting in preventive and mitigation efforts. One of the preventive measures for the identified risks was to verify and validate the current well conditions, while mitigation efforts included narrowing the leakage area and installing a hydrocarbon detector.

1. Introduction

The world's continued need for gas and oil is demonstrated by the existence of offshore platforms, which are already quite common and will only grow in number. Over 7,500 oil and gas platforms have been installed globally, situated in the continental regions of 53 countries, 40 of which are major producers of natural gas and oil [1]. Among the 53 nations whose territories produce and have installed offshore gas and oil platforms is Indonesia. According to the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources' statistical data report from 2021, production of crude oil totaled 658.54 million Barrels of Oil per Day (BOPD), while production of natural gas was 1,178 million BOPD. Oil and gas exploitation operations typically use a variety of offshore platform types, including semi-submersible, TLP, SPAR, FPSO, and others. It is more common with fixed offshore platforms in Indonesia itself (Jacket). This is due to the relatively shallow depth of the Indonesian waters, which range from 0 to 300 meters [2].

The government governs the Technical Guidelines for the Dismantling of Offshore Oil and Gas Installations by Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources Regulation Number 01 of 2011. The process of removing all or a portion of the installation and relocating the components to a designated location is known as dismantling or decommissioning. Decommissioning offshore platforms that are no longer in service or operational is necessary to prevent disruptions to shipping, navigation, or other operations [3]. According to the ministerial regulation, decommissioning also serves to protect the environment,

the safety of oil and gas companies, the upkeep of the installation's state inventory, and the best possible use of the products in the state inventory. In order to enable offshore platforms to be used as artificial reefs and cut expenses and procedures after their equipment is decommissioned, the government has also issued regulations regarding the conversion of buildings and installations at sea. There is a significant risk of mishaps and malfunctions when decommissioning offshore oil and gas platforms. According to statistical data from SKK Migas, there is a high risk of work accidents in the upstream oil and gas sector. To control potential risks, risk analysis is required prior to decommissioning activities. To put it simply, risk analysis is the process of identifying threats and vulnerabilities, evaluating them to make sure the decommissioning will have the desired effects, and emphasizing how those effects can be minimized or eliminated.

Figure 1. Jacket Platform MWP-C

The author of this study aims to perform a risk analysis on figure 1 manifold wellhead platform-C (MWP-C) decommissioning process in the Peciko field. Decommissioning is required because this platform has been in use for more than 20 years and could cease to function at any time.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Decommissioning

Decommissioning or dismantling is the activity of removing part or all of the installation and transporting the results of the decommissioning to a predetermined location. Decommissioning of offshore platforms is carried out if:

- The age of the offshore platform has exceeded the predetermined design life.
- The platform has stopped operating and/or there is damage that cannot be repaired and is not in accordance with regulations.
- Oil and gas wells are no longer productive.

The objectives of decommissioning offshore platforms are:

- Ensuring the safety of oil and gas in Indonesia.
- Implementation of environmental management.
- Maintaining asset conditions.
- Maintaining the safety of shipping activities.

2.2 Fuzzy-FMEA

As time has gone on, a number of specialists have discovered flaws in the traditional FMEA method. Experts have identified a few shortcomings with traditional FMEA as follows: a. Due to the multiplication of Severity (S), Occurrence (O), and Detection (D), it is possible for different failure modes to have the same RPN [4]. b. Each of the three criteria—S, O, and D—has the same weight and no weighting [5]. c. The indirect relationship between criteria is not taken into account when multiplying S, O, and D to obtain RPN [6]. These experts have identified certain weaknesses, which can be addressed by using a fuzzy logic approach to weight S, O, and D. Based on the outcomes of each criterion—S, O, and D—which are transformed into linguistic variables, fuzzy logic is utilized to replace the index ranking in the FMEA. The IF-THEN rule is then applied to produce fuzzy RPN output [7]

Figure 2. Fuzzy-FMEA [8]

Figure 2 is skem for fuzzy FMEA in fuzzification, in the context of Fuzzy-FMEA, is the process of redefining the crisp criteria's severity, occurrence, and detection functions to become fuzzy severity, fuzzy occurrence, and fuzzy detection [9]. After the fuzzy rule is applied, the rule evaluation task is completed using the IF-THEN IF-FLUID rule base that has already been created. This step will involve defuzzification, or redefining fuzzy to crisp, which will be produced by Fuzzy-RPN using a combination of the original fuzzy criteria.

3. Analysis Data

3.1 FFMEA

Fuzzy consists of three main panels: output (blue box), rule evaluation (white box), and input (yellow box) in Figure 3. This step involves mapping the membership functions of crisp number variables into linguistic variables for input, such as output, occurrence, severity, and detection. Five linguistic variables are used to map the input: very low (VL), low (L), medium (M), high (H), and very high (VH). Ten linguistic variables are used to define the output: none (N), low (L), high low (HL), low medium (LM), medium (M), high medium (HM), low high (LH), high (H), and very high (VH). Expert-set fuzzy rule bases, or fuzzy rule bases, or fuzzy rule bases (FRBs), are necessary for rule evaluation.

Figure 3. Fuzzification

The surface graph in Figures 4, 5 and 6 illustrates the relationship between each input severity, occurrence, and detection. A fuzzy-RPN will be produced on the z axis by combining the numbers entered for each parameter on the xy axis.

Figure 4. Correlation between Severity and Detection

Figure 5. Correlation between Severity and Occurance

Figure 6. Correlation between Occurance and Detection

When compared to other parameters on fuzzy-RPN, the severity parameter has the greatest significance, according to the surface graph in Figures 4 and 5. When the detection and occurrence parameters' input values are set to 1, the severity parameter's input value can be traced to a value of 10, which allows it to reach fuzzy-RPN 7, a high-risk category. When both the occurrence and detection parameters in Figure 6 are valued at 10, the combined results of their input values only yield a fuzzy-RPN value of 7. This is a result of the platform dismantling process placing a higher priority on worker and asset safety and security than on the likelihood of a hazard occurring and the ease of detecting it. The ease of detecting hazards is more important than the likelihood that they will occur because, on the one hand, the likelihood of an incident cannot influence the ease of detecting hazards, and, on the other hand, the ease of detecting hazards will influence the likelihood of an incident.

Table 1. Calculation RPN

No	Activity	Code	S	O	D	RPN	Rank	FRPN	Rank
1	Marine Operations	1a	5	2	5	50	14	4.33	17
		1b	7	1	3	21	18	5.46	12
		1c	3	2	3	18	19	3.28	20
		1d	5	1	3	15	20	4.41	16
		1e	5	3	4	60	12	4.53	15
2	Well Plug and Abandonment	2a	10	4	9	360	1	9	1
3	Equipment Decomm	3a	7	3	5	105	9	6.22	6
		3b	7	4	5	140	7	6.21	7
		3c	5	3	5	75	11	4.55	14
4	Pipeline Decomm	4a	8	4	8	256	3	7.39	3
		4b	3	4	3	36	16	3.59	19
5	Conductor Decomm	5a	4	3	4	48	15	4.21	18
6	Topside Decomm	6a	6	5	5	150	5	6	10
		6b	8	1	7	56	13	7.16	4
		6c	7	5	6	210	4	6.33	5
7	Jacket Decomm	7a	6	4	6	144	6	5.68	11
8	Lifting Operation	8a	7	2	7	98	10	6.17	9
		8b	9	5	8	360	1	8.07	2
		8c	7	5	4	140	7	6.21	8
9	Diving (ROV, Diver)	9a	3	1	2	6	22	2.8	21
		9b	6	2	3	36	16	5.12	13
10	Site Clearance	10a	1	3	3	9	21	1.99	22

Based on the RPN calculation in Table 1, the failure mode of residual hydrocarbon leakage and its impact of explosion and fire on the platform and operation location with FRPN 9 and classical RPN 360 represents the highest failure risk with fuzzy-RPN and classical RPN. The failure mode in the lifting process and its impact of worker accidents (object impact) with FRPN 8.07 and classical RPN 360 represents the second highest RPN, and the failure mode in the pipeline cutting process and its impact of explosion due to residual hydrocarbon trapped in the pipe with FRPN 7.39 and classical RPN 256 defines the third highest RPN. It is evident from the comparison table between the fuzzy-RPN and classical RPN ranking results that the classical RPN ranking method still has issues with ranking because the results are multiplied by the same parameters. This is not the same as fuzzy-RPN, which ranks dominant risks accurately and produces different results by applying the fuzzyfication and defuzzyfication processes to the input parameter values.

3.2 FTA

The MWP-C Platform decommissioning process uses failure risk analysis (FTA) to identify the underlying causes of the failure modes found in the earlier analysis [10,11,12]. Critical risks are identified as top intermediate events in the FTA method based on the three failure modes that have the highest RPN obtained from the fuzzy FMEA method [13,14]. Remaining hydrocarbon leakage, lifting process failure, and pipeline cutting process failure are the three failure modes. To find the fundamental event that can lead to the top event, the three most significant events will be dissected.

3.2.1 Risk of Residual Hydrocarbon Leak Failure

There are two main categories of causes for residual hydrocarbon leakage: poor planning and preparation and poor sealing. These elements are acquired by literacy and expert consultation. The explanation of risk factors is as follows:

a. Planning and Preparation Errors

Inadequate planning and preparation can have disastrous effects on the exploitation well closure procedure. Inaccurate well reports lead to incorrect equipment and technical calculations, and the use of the wrong P&A techniques will deteriorate the well foundation [15,16].

b. Sealing Failure

Cracks in the isolation cement, deformation of the well casing, and the use of materials in the well barrier with a porosity larger than the hydrocarbon can all contribute to sealing failure or the inability to isolate exploitation wells.

3.2.2 Risk of Failure of Lifting Process

Errors in lifting load calculation and damage to lifting equipment are the two main categories of causes of lifting process failure. These elements are acquired by literacy and expert consultation. The following is a description of the risk factors:

a. Lifting Equipment Damage

Damage to lifting equipment such as padeye, sling, crane will hinder the process of lifting the platform section to the barge. In this case, damage that can occur such as cracked padeye due to lack of maintenance, broken sling due to the load being lifted not being in accordance with the sling's capacity, and crane arms that can experience fatigue due to unstable lifting movements.

b. Lifting Load Calculation Error

The calculation of lifting load can possibly be wrong due to differences in the report data obtained with real conditions in the field. This will result in the lifting process being hampered and the movement of unstable objects which risk falling objects.

3.2.3 Risk of Pipeline Cutting Process Failure

Diver error and impediments in the pigging process are the two main causes of the failure risk associated with the pipeline cutting process. These elements are acquired by literacy and expert consultation. The following is a description of the risk factors:

a. Diver Error

Diver error is an error in implementation by divers who are cutting the pipeline. SOPs that are not violated and divers' unpreparedness to face extreme conditions can cause failure in the pipeline cutting process.

b. Obstacles in the pigging process

One of the processes in cutting the pipeline is pigging which aims to clean up the remaining hydrocarbons and debris in the pipeline. When there are obstacles in the pigging process in the middle of the pipeline, it will certainly hinder the pipeline cutting process, the cause of which is that the pigs are stuck due to the accumulation of debris so that it stops the speed of the pigs and is also caused by buckling in the pipe.

3.2.4 Probability

According to the probability calculation in Table 2, the probability of failure of the MWP-C Platform decommissioning process is 0.00399791, with the failure mode with the highest probability being the lifting process failure, which has a probability value of 0.00218440. The lifting process has a high probability of failure due to its length and the presence of a variety of lifting objects, both light and heavy.

Table 2. Probabilty Minimum Cutset

No	Code	Event	Probability
1	A.1	Planning and Preparation Errors	0,00026645
2	A.2	<i>Sealing failure</i>	0,00044118
	A	Residual Hydrocarbon Leak Failure	0,00070751
1	B.1	Lifting Equipment Damage	0,00172520
2	B.2	Lifting Load Calculation Error	0,00046000
	B	Failure of Lifting Process	0,00218440
1	C.1	<i>Diver error</i>	0,00021275
2	C.2	Obstacles in the pigging process	0,00089819
	C	Pipeline Cutting Process Failure	0,00111075
	Top Event	The MWP-C Platform decommissioning process	0,00399791

4. Conclusions

The MWP-C Platform decommissioning process is most likely to fail due to residual hydrocarbon leakage (FRPN 9), lifting process failure (FRPN 8.07), and pipeline cutting process failure (FRPN 7.39). The root causes of the failure of the decommissioning process on the MWP-C Platform were identified using FTA, which included residual hydrocarbon leakage, the use of the incorrect P&A method, invalid well reports, cement cracking, casing deformation, and porous barriers. The lifting process failed due to padeye cracking, broken sling ropes, crane arm fatigue, and lifting load calculation errors. And the pipeline cutting process failed because SOPs were not followed, diving equipment became jammed, ROVs malfunctioned, debris accumulated, free span, lateral buckling, and upheaval buckling.

References

- [1] Parente, V., Ferreira, D. & Santos, E., 2006. "Offshore decommissioning issues: Deductibility and transferability". *Energy Policy*, **34**(15), pp. 1992-2001.

- [2] Sadeghi, K., 2007. "An Overview of Design, Analysis, Construction and Installation of Offshore Petroleum Platforms Suitable for Cyprus Oil/Gas Fields". *Social & Application Science*, Volume **4**, pp. 1-16.
- [3] Claisse, J. T. & Love, M. S., 2015. "Impact from Partial Removal of Decommissioning Oil and Gas Platforms on Fish Biomass and Production on the Remaining Platform Structure and Surrounding Shell Mounds". *PLoS ONE*, Volume **10**.
- [4] Kumru, M. & Kumru, P. Y., 2013. "Fuzzy FMEA Application to Improve Purchasing Process in a Public Hospital". *Applied Soft Computing*, Volume **13**, pp. 721-733.
- [5] Hadi-Vencheh, A. & Aghajani, M., 2013. "Failure Mode and Effect Analysis A Fuzzy Group MCDM Approach". *Journal of Soft Computing and Applications*, pp. 1-4.
- [6] Chang, K. H. & Cheng, C. H., 2010. "A Risk Assessment Methodology Using Intuitionistic Fuzzy set in FMEA". *International Journal of System Science*, Volume **41**, pp. 1457-1471.
- [7] Dhanistha, W. L., Silvianita, S., & Wardhana, W. (2018). Wave height prediction based fuzzy logic. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, **9**(9), 1611–1616.
- [8] Yeh, R. H. & Hsieh, M. H., 2007. "Fuzzy Assessment of FMEA for a Sewage Plant". *Journal of The Chinese Institute of Industrial Engineers*, Volume **24**, pp. 505-512.
- [9] Yeh, R.H. and Hsieh, M. H.: Fuzzy Assessment of FMEA for a Sewage Plant. *Journal of The Chinese Institute of Industrial Engineers* **4**(1): 505-512 10.1016/j.promfg.2015.11.041.
- [10] Silvianita, Mahandeka, D.S., Rosyid, D.M.: Fault Tree Analysis for Investigation on the Causes of Project Problems. *Procedia Earth and Planetary Science* **14**: 213-219, 2015 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeps.2015.07.104>
- [11] Rausand, M.: *Risk Assessment: Theory, Methods, and Application*. Wiley, USA, 2011.
- [12] Nugroho, E.N., Sunbara, A.: Work Accident Analysis in the Construction Project of PT. XYZ. *International Journal of New Technology and Research* **7**(2): 44-56 2021 <https://doi.org/10.31871/IJNTR.7.2.7>
- [13] Ericson, C. A., 2005. Hazard Analysis Techniques for System Safety. Hoboken, New Jersey: Wiley-Interscience
- [14] Zhong, C., Chen, Z., and Zhou, J.: Numerical Investigations of Pile Group Foundations under Different Pile Length Conditions. *Applied Sciences* **14**(5): 1908, 2024 <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14051908>
- [15] Efstathopoulos, G. E., & Balomenos, G. P.: Effects of wave load models on the uplift fragility assessment of pile-supported wharves and piers exposed to storm surge and waves. *Engineering Structures*, **290**: 116372 2023 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENGSTRUCT.2023.116372>
- [16] Yetkin, M.E., Özfirat, M.K., Kun, M., and Pamukcu, C.: The prediction of the risks of spontaneous combustion in underground coal mines using a fault tree analysis method. *MethodsX* **13**: 102835, 2024 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mex.2024.102835>